

THE EFFECT OF INCREASED OCCLUSAL LOAD IN BRUXISM AND PATHOLOGICAL ABRASION OF HARD DENTAL TISSUES ON PROCESSES IN PERIODONTAL TISSUES**Mammadova S.***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Associate Professor
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Baku, Azerbaijan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7326994>**Abstract**

Bruxism is characterized by the formation of pathological abrasion of hard dental tissues of various clinical forms and severity with a number of pathological morpho-functional changes in the dental system. Increased occlusal load, in addition to changes in the anatomical shape of the tooth, causes pathological changes in periodontal tissues.

Keywords: Bruxism, pathological tooth wear

According to different authors, the prevalence of pathological abrasion of hard dental tissues ranges from 4 to 57% at a young age, reaches 91% in older people [1, 4] and is accompanied by both morphological and functional disorders of the dentition, accompanying pathological abrasion of teeth, consider both dysfunctional disorders of the temporomandibular joints [3], changes in the bioelectric activity of masticatory muscles [2], and changes in the microcirculatory bed of periodontal tissues of the teeth that hold the bite height. The clinical picture is significantly more complicated in the presence of bruxism [5, 6]. One of the methods for diagnosing changes in microcirculation is laser Doppler flowmetry (LDF), based on determining the rhythmic components of hemodynamic flows in the areas under study.

Since orthopedic methods for the treatment of pathological abrasion of hard tissues of the teeth primarily involve an increase in the height of the occlusion, which entails an increased occlusal load on the supporting teeth at the stages of adaptation, determining the state and degree of pathological changes in the microvasculature of the periodontal tissues of the supporting teeth will allow, taking into account the compensatory capabilities of the supporting teeth, teeth to predict the course of adaptation to an increase in the height of the occlusion and to predict periodontal complications.

Material and research methods

To achieve the goal, 100 patients aged 18 to 65 years with pathological abrasion of hard dental tissues of varying degrees and a control group of patients of the same age period with intact dentition and physiological forms of bite were examined using clinical and special research methods. Bruxism from the specified contingent was diagnosed in 20 people. Depending on the degree of pathological abrasion, the patients were divided into the following clinical groups: group 1 - 27 patients with a pathological lesion depth of up to 1/3 of the crown length; group 2 - 28 patients with a lesion depth from 1/3 to 2/3 of the crown length; group 3 - 21 patients with a lesion depth from 2/3 to the gums. The 4th group - the control group - included 24 patients with physiological forms of abrasion of the crowns of the teeth within the enamel. Bruxism was diagnosed by the

number of bruxism episodes using the BiteStrip device (Germany) for periodontal teeth with varying degrees of pathological abrasion. Laser Doppler flowmetry (LDF) was performed on a LAKK-02 apparatus (NPP Lazma) with a program for recording and processing microcirculation parameters - LDF, version 1.18 dated 20.6.99. Measurements were taken in the supine position at least three hours after eating or chewing gum. The total microvascular blood flow of periodontal tissues was determined by the following parameters: integral characteristic of the movement of erythrocytes in the volume of the probing tissue - PM (pf units); standard deviation of the oscillation amplitude from the average value of the PM (σ); coefficient of vasomotor activity of microvessels (Kv, %); reserve of capillary circulation - RKK; microcirculation efficiency index - IEM. The level of microcirculation of the mucous membrane of the oral cavity of the tooth was determined in the projection of areas of teeth with pathological and physiological forms of wear, namely: alveolar gums, marginal gums, as well as a transitional fold. Measurements were taken in the projection of the tooth root. The obtained results were processed using the LAK V02.EXE software package and the par dbf.exe converter. Data analysis and processing was carried out using the STATISTICA 12 MS Excel XP application package.

Results of the study and their discussion According to the results of the analysis of studies, it was found that, compared with the control group, the level of capillary blood flow in bruxism, depending on the degree of pathological wear of the teeth, changed significantly. The indicators of microcirculation parameters of patients with pathological abrasion of hard dental tissues were determined in comparison with patients of the control group.

In patients with the first degree of pathological abrasion of hard tissues of the teeth, complicated by bruxism, while maintaining the anatomical shape of the teeth, a significant increase in the level of microcirculation of the periodontal tissues of the supporting teeth was found compared with the control, which can be explained by an increase in the metabolic meostasis of the periodontal tissues of the compensatory-adaptive

mechanisms for regulating tissue circulation in response to the increased occlusal load characteristic of bruxism. With the loss of the anatomical shape of the teeth (up to 2/3 of the length of the crown in patients of the second clinical group and the level of the gums in patients of the third clinical group), the parameters of microcirculation in the studied areas also changed significantly. In particular, the parameter of microcirculation of marginal gums in the 3rd group was significantly lower than that of the alveolar gums in the 4th group, namely 16.0 ± 0.31 (pf. units) versus 20 ± 0.16 (pf. units .)) respectively. The same trend was observed in the indicators obtained at the level of the transitional fold. The decrease in blood circulation rate in this category of patients can be explained by dystrophic processes, a decrease in the reserve capacity of microvessels of periodontal tissues, due to the lack of perception of the optimal functional masticatory load by periodontal tissues as a result of the loss of the anatomical shape of the crowns of the teeth, often with the bite of some cases. in areas of periodontal teeth with severe pathological abrasion, the presence of chronic inflammation with the formation of granulomas and cystogranulomas was observed, which can be explained by a reaction to functional overload.

Conclusions

1. In the case of functional overload of periodontal tissues in patients with bruxism in the initial forms of pathological abrasion of tooth crowns, an increase in the level of microcirculation of periodontal tissues of supporting teeth and a significant decrease in the PM of alveolar gums to 16.0 ± 0.31 are observed. ± 0.16 (pf. units) in the control with a significant loss of tooth crowns and a decrease in bite height.

2. Changes in the vascularization of the periodontal tissues of the teeth with a significant loss of the crown part indicates the need for the timely application of a complex of therapeutic and preventive measures.

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